

Identifying water consumption profiles through unsupervised clustering of household timeseries: the case of Attica, Greece

Nikos PELEKANOS¹, Georgios MORAITIS¹, Panagiotis DIMAS¹, Panagiotis KOSSIERIS¹, Christos MAKROPOULOS¹

¹ Dept. of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, National Technical University of Athens
email: npelekanos@mail.ntua.gr; georgemoraitis@mail.ntua.gr; pdimas@mail.ntua.gr; pkossier@central.ntua.gr; cmakro@mail.ntua.gr

ABSTRACT

Urban water systems are complex, socio-technical systems, tasked with meeting water demands, generated through a continuous (socio-technical) interplay between customers and infrastructure, maintaining high reliability levels. Understanding demand patterns at different scales, is thus essential to manage the associated water distribution infrastructure and better serve customers. Here, we analyse water consumption data from 40 municipalities in Attica, Greece, served by the water company of Athens, EYDAP S.A., using machine learning techniques to detect principal patterns in water consumption. The data, which were extracted and provided by EYDAP S.A., are monthly time series of consumption points between 2010 and 2021, a sample which is analysed through an unsupervised data clustering process, to gain insights on dominant consumption patterns and to identify characteristic customer profiles.

1. Introduction

Adaptive urban water management, especially within a context of resilient smart cities, prompts utilities to adopt hydro-informatic approaches to understand past, manage present and (to the extent possible) predict future consumption behaviour of their customers (Makropoulos and Savić 2019). Detecting trends, similarities, and differences and grouping customers under homogenous consumption profiles, allows utilities and regulators to design better, more pro-active water demand management strategies. However, geographical or social aggregation criteria may lead to information loss, as inhomogeneous consumptions are blended to form a “characteristic consumption profile” for each criterion of reference. To overcome such biases, this work applies unsupervised data clustering techniques, resulting in an evidence-based, data-driven identification of principal consumption profiles for the examined regions in Attica.

2. Methodology

We utilized a dataset comprising of 120,000 consumption point timeseries at monthly step, covering the period from Apr-2010 to Aug-2021. The selection was made by picking 3000 points from 40 different municipalities of Attica, Greece with the sole condition being that in each timestep the consumption should be under 25 m³/month, thus assuming only household level consumers for all timeseries. As a pre-processing step, each sequence of our 120,000 sample dataset was normalized utilizing the Z-score:

$$y'_i = \frac{y_i - \bar{x}}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{x} is the mean and σ is the standard deviation of each timeseries y_i (for $i = 1:120,000$). The purpose of this scaling reflects the need of fitting our dataset in an uninformative range, allowing for an unbiased (from average) water consumption pattern comparison in a width-invariant way.

For the timeseries segmentation, we applied a k-means type unsupervised algorithm in which the default ‘Euclidean’ distance measure was replaced by the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) (Petitjean et al. 2011) as more suitable to sequential values distance metrics. Intuitively, DTW expresses a measure of similarity between two temporal sequences (i.e., consumption timeseries), where their shapes ‘match’, regardless of temporal shifts. The DTW equation can be expressed as follows:

$$DTW(x, y) = \min_{\pi} \sqrt{\sum_{(i,j) \in \pi} d(x_i, y_j)^2} \quad (2)$$

where $\pi = [\pi_0, \dots, \pi_k]$ is a path that satisfies more complex conditions, the detailed explanation of which is included in the work Berndt and Clifford (1994). The selection of the optimal number k of clusters was

estimated through a preliminary assessment, by exploring various k components of Gaussian Mixture Modelling approaches and scoring each realisation by estimating its corresponding Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The lower BIC score resulted for a $k = 30$ cluster segmentation, which is assumed optimal.

Fig. 1. 30 characteristic consumption profiles in the Attica region, derived through unsupervised clustering of 120,000 measurement points. Darker blue areas show lower consumption and lighter yellow areas show consumption peaks per profile.

Finally, for each cluster created, a characteristic timeseries (profile) representing the overall cluster shape was created by averaging the scaled monthly values of each cluster timeseries set. The homogenised cluster behaviour for the derived consumption profiles is presented in Fig. 1. Each characteristic timeseries was decomposed into three components: trend, seasonality, and residual (noise) (Fig. 2). Additionally, for each cluster, the percentage of inclusion of each municipality is calculated, a tactic which enables us to observe dominant patterns in some municipalities.

Fig. 2. Decomposition of the characteristic timeseries from Cluster 10 and 14.

3. Discussion and concluding remarks

We analysed an extensive dataset of point consumption timeseries and produced the characteristic consumption profiles, which summarize the behaviour of 30 distinct clustered customer groups in the water supply system of Attika, Greece. These profiles can be utilized to model the consumption of the region, as a surrogate training dataset for demand forecasting, as well as a template to produce synthetic consumer demands in unmetered regions and/or District Metered Areas (DMAs) for design or optimal control purposes.

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References

- Berndt, D. J., and Clifford, J. (1994). "Using Dynamic Time Warping to Find Patterns in Time Series." Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, AAAIWS'94, AAAI Press, 359–370.
- Makropoulos, C., and Savić, D. A. (2019). "Urban hydroinformatics: Past, present and future." *Water (Switzerland)*, 11(10).
- Petitjean, F., Ketterlin, A., and Gançarski, P. (2011). "A global averaging method for dynamic time warping, with applications to clustering." *Pattern Recognition*, 44(3), 678–693.